

PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND DIRECTIONS

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Abstract. *In this study, we believe that the use of innovative pedagogical theories of education is desirable when using modern innovative methods in education. The reason is that the form of collaborative education based on innovative education based on effective educational programs is currently yielding good results. There is an opportunity to improve the quality of education by applying new pedagogical methods and new educational theories in the education system. Theoretical data on the use of pedagogical methods based on modern innovative educational programs are presented.*

Keywords: *Innovative education, pedagogical methods, curriculum, collaborative learning, innovative pedagogy, teaching techniques.*

TA'LIM METODLARI VA YO'NALISHLARINING AMALIYOTDA QO'LLANILISHI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda ta'limda zamonaviy innovatsion metodlardan foydalanishda asosan innovatsion pedagogik ta'lim nazariyalaridan foydalanish afzal deb hisoblaymiz. Sababi samarali ta'lim dasturlariga asoslangan holda innovatsion ta'limga asoslangan ta'limning kolloborativ shakli hozirda yaxshi natija bermoqda. Ta'lim tizimida yangi pedagogik metodlardan foydalanish va yangi ta'limga oid nazariyalardan foydalanish orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirish imkoniyati mavjud. Zamonaviy innovatsion ta'lim dasturlariga asoslangan pedagogik metodlardan foydalanish bo'yicha nazariy ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Innovatsion ta'lim, pedagogik metodlar, ta'lim dasturi, kolloborativ ta'lim, innovatsion pedagogika, o'qitish texnikasi.*

Introduction

In the current era of globalization, the socio-economic development of society, technological progress, and the expansion of information flows require new approaches to the education system. The concept of innovative pedagogy occupies a central place in the educational process and is of great importance in the formation of modern teaching technologies, new theoretical concepts, and creative teaching methods. Innovative pedagogy is a scientific and practical direction aimed at introducing innovations into pedagogical activity, effectively organizing the teaching process, and developing the intellectual, creative, and spiritual potential of the individual.

This approach is primarily associated with creating new foundations for the relationship between the teacher and the student, focusing education on the individual, encouraging independent thinking, and using the capabilities of digital technologies. Innovative pedagogy involves a radical renewal not only of teaching methods, but also of the entire education system, improving the professional qualifications of teachers, and harmonizing curricula with the requirements of the time.

Therefore, this article focuses on the essence of innovative pedagogy, its main theories, the importance of innovative approaches in the educational process, and their application in practice.

The educational result of the student's individual work in the formation of his own knowledge is supported by group and collective activities. The student shares resources with the group, uses group work for learning. The structure of the activity is flexible and open, and a collaborative situation such as search is further formed. The teacher plays the role of a facilitator in learning, and the group acts as a source of information, motivation, a means of self-help and mutual assistance, and a special place of interaction for the formation of collective knowledge. In cooperative education, there is no a priori distribution of roles, as in simple joint (cooperative) work. Individuals gradually unite into a group, which gradually becomes a whole, and its potential is greater than the sum of its parts, which often allows for high-quality work. At the same time, there is both individual responsibility for the common work and the responsibility of the entire team. All members of the group are in close and constant contact, each brings to the group their own joint efforts, each can contribute to increasing the productivity of other members of the group and thereby adhere to the principle of continuous improvement of each of their work.

Development in cooperation is carried out within the framework of the task and the project as a whole. The mutual cooperation of group members is long-term, and coordination of the team helps to achieve the ultimate goal. For greater coordination between group members, the number of its participants should not exceed five people. Often, when older students and sometimes teachers hear the term collaborative learning, they automatically associate it with a negative context of working in groups, which can cause problems in the school environment. Methods and mechanisms based on collaborative learning encourage them to abandon the concept of collaboration (old methods), which they consider unrealistic or an attempt to shift the learning load from the teacher to the students. In open distance learning, we must reiterate the benefits of collaborative work and the need to support each of its participants, especially in terms of motivational dynamics, where the external aspect is necessary for success. This initial concern of some students is noteworthy, because based on multi-vector learning, it is an example of a misunderstanding that has become an absolutely indispensable approach to the greatest viability of teaching and learning in digital networks. The following principles can be used in the selection and gradual implementation of collaborative learning mechanisms, as well as in cooperative learning. The results of students working together lead to mutual understanding, and, perhaps, we can provide a more effective learning process than if we worked alone. Oral and written communication between students helps to achieve the best understanding. Through the experience of living in a cooperative learning program, students' ability to recognize the relationship between social interaction and better mutual understanding is further formed.

It is necessary to determine the state of understanding of certain elements of deep mastery of the topic during the lesson, specific and unpredictable information. We are putting forward the idea that participation in games based on new innovative ideas in improving cooperative skills should provide voluntariness and freedom, but at the same time it should be firmly supported. It is clear that the cooperative learning mode requires a wider participation of stakeholders. The ability of a group to develop this human capital is perceived by some as a sign of collective intelligence.

According to Pierre Levy, collective intelligence is a globally distributed intelligence, since no one knows everything, but everyone knows something. Knowledge is present in a person, and not in some transcendent entity that organizes its wider distribution in society; therefore, a well-organized team is recognized as the main human wealth, personally coordinated in real time.

In the direction of pedagogy, the mechanism for organizing multi-vector educational models is similar to cooperative learning and learning through collaborative methods focused on the importance of interaction between members of a small group - students. The goal of cooperative (collective) forms of education is the transition from simple educational actions to a group form of organizing learning. As for the definition of the concepts of "teaching with pedagogical methods in the development of cooperative skills" and "collaborative teaching based on multi-vector approaches", there are definitions that emphasize their difference and definitions that are consistent with the concept of "collaborative teaching based on multi-vector directions".

It is desirable that the intellectual efforts of students are combined in groups of 2 or more people to search for explanations, solutions and create a teaching methodology. In this article, the term "collaborative learning" is used in its unifying meaning. The collaborative process should have the following characteristics. First, this can be achieved through the correct use of methods in the direction of reflective pedagogy. The lack of instructions and structures in the methods can lead to difficulties in achieving learning goals. High quality of education is ensured by setting clear learning goals. The second characteristic of collaborative learning is the duration of cooperation. In collaborative learning activities, all group members must work together to achieve the goals. That is, if one group member does all the work, he or she is not learning collaboratively.

Regardless of whether all members of the group are given the same task or whether participants are working together on different tasks that make up one large project, all students must share the learning responsibilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that, taking into account the results of innovative pedagogy implemented through teaching techniques, the assimilation of new knowledge by students during the lesson should be meaningful, which contributes to the formation of a deep understanding of the subject, the ability to find connections between objects and phenomena, as well as the ability to associate new information with existing knowledge. Thus, cooperative learning is one of the most convenient and effective ways to ensure the activity of two or more groups of students working together and evenly distributing the workload in accordance with the intended learning outcomes. In addition to social and psychological aspects, two factors related to the cognitive sphere can contribute to the effectiveness of cooperative learning - the choice of a well-thought-out task and the use of methodologies that help increase the level of mental effort required for learning activities.

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